

ISic1293

I.Sicily inscription 1293

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140783

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) .
2. Δάφνη γλυ[κυ]-
3. τάτη, χαῖρ[ε. ἔζη]-
4. σας ἔτη [—' — —]
5. τύχης Ν [— — — —]
6. Οἶ πεπ [ρωμεν— —]
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492897

EDCS 39101662

PHI 140783

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0469 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5703

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